

MANUFACTURING SECTOR AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Manufacturing sector, economic growth, Nigeria, exchange rate, inflation rate, interest rate, gross domestic product (GDP)

Abstract: This study examines the impact of manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria. The research is a quantitative research and time series and secondary data was used for the study over a period of 33 years from 1990 to 2023. Secondary data was used extracted from the CBN Statistical bulletin (2023). E-Views software was used to analyse the variables. The adopted the ARDL model as a technique for analysis. The study used GDP as the dependent variable and manufacturing sector output, exchange rate, inflation rate and interest rate as the independent variables. It was concluded that a significant positive relationship exists between manufacturing sector output and economic growth in Nigeria. It was recommended that government should encourage the growth of industries in Nigeria through establishment of favourable policies for industrial growth and development. The study also recommend that government should intensify effort at improving physical infrastructure notably in power supply and make it more accessible to manufacturers to reduce self-supply of electricity which brings huge operating cost. This suggests that economic openness and the interest rate must be combined with other vital factors to give the desired boost to industrialization development which in turn benefit the manufacturing sector and improve economic growth in Nigeria.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

There has been a growing concern on the role of fiscal policy on the output and input of manufacturing industry in Nigeria, despite the fact that the government had embarked on several policies aimed at improving the growth of Nigerian economy through the contribution of manufacturing industry to the economy and

capacity utilization of the sector. In literature, Libanio (2006) through the use of Kaldor's first law defined manufacturing sector as the engine of growth of the economy. Manufacturing sector refers to those industries which are involved in the manufacturing and processing of items and indulge in either creation of new commodities or in value addition (Adebayo, 2010). To Dickson (2010), manufacturing

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sector accounts for a significant share of the industrial sector in developed countries. The final products can either serve as finished goods for sale to customers or as intermediate goods used in the production process. Manufacturing sector (Loto, 2012) refers to an avenue for increasing productivity in relation to import replacement and export expansion, creating foreign exchange earning capacity, raising employment and per capita income which causes unrepeatable consumption pattern. Mbelede (2012) opined that manufacturing sector is involved in the process of adding value to raw materials by turning them into product. Thus, manufacturing industries is the key variable in an economy and motivates conversion of raw material into finished goods. In the work of Charles (2012), manufacturing industries creates employment which helps to boost agriculture and diversify the economy on the process of helping the nation to increase its foreign exchange earnings. Manufacturing industries came into being with the occurrence of technological and socio-economic transformations in the Western countries in the 18th-19th centuries. This period was widely known as industrial revolution. It all began in Britain and replaced the labor-intensive textile production with mechanization and use of fuels. Manufacturing sector are categorized into engineering sector, construction sector, electronics sector, chemical sector, energy sector, textile sector, food and beverage sector, metalworking sector, plastic sector, transport and telecommunication sector. In recent time, some manufacturing industries in Nigeria have been

characterized by declining productivity rate, by extension employment generation, which is caused largely by inadequate electricity supply, smuggling of foreign products into the country, trade liberalisation, globalisation, high exchange rate, and low government expenditure. Therefore, the slow performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria is mainly due to massive importation of finished goods and inadequate financial support, which has resulted in the reduction in capacity utilization and input of the manufacturing sector in the economy (Tomola, Adebisi and Olawale, 2012). Furthermore, in Nigeria, the level of growth in manufacturing sector has been affected negatively because of high interest rate on lending and this high lending rate is responsible for high cost of production in country's manufacturing sector (Adebiyi, 2001; Adebiyi and Babatope, 2004; Rasheed, 2010). Hence, Okafor (2012) observed that the level of Nigerian manufacturing industries' performance will continue to decline because of low implementation of government budget and difficulties in assessing raw materials and stiff competition with foreign firms. From 1982 to 1986, Nigeria's value added in manufacturing fell considerably partly because of inefficient resources allocation caused by distorted prices and prohibition of importation. Between 1986 to 1988, the World Bank induced structural adjustment program (SAP) in the economy's economy contributed to larger increase in manufacturing industry contribution to GDP, which grew 8 percent in 1988. The deregulation of foreign exchange market was also reckoned to make manufacturing industries more

competitive by increasing input costs (CBN, 2010). Looking at the manufacturing sector share in the GDP in recent years (1990-2010), it has not been relatively stable. In 1990, it was about 5.5% while it drops to 2.22% in 2010. This changes in manufacturing share in GDP and capacity utilization shows that firms that are efficient can contribute to job creation, technology promotion and as well ensure equitable distribution of economic opportunities and the macroeconomic stability of the country. Recently, government policies began to show more concern on the management and improvement of the economy. Government over the years embarks on various macroeconomic policy options to grow the economy in terms of growth and development and the policy option employed is that of fiscal policy (Peter and Simeon, 2011). Based on the nature and importance of the relationship between fiscal policy and manufacturing sector, the study becomes necessary in Nigeria where output and capacity utilization of manufacturing sector have suffered rapid fluctuations in recent years. Since government desires to increase total spending in the economy with fiscal policy which can either increase it's spending or reduce taxes in maintaining manufacturing sector stability, it is therefore the researcher's interest to investigate the impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector of Nigerian economy. Thus, this is the focus of this seminar paper.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Literature on manufacturing industry performance, both theoretical and empirical is

tremendous. Upon several government policies on the stability of Nigerian economy through manufacturing industry, there has been a lot of challenges facing the growth of Nigerian manufacturing industry as identify by researchers. These challenges include: corruption and ineffective economic policies (Gbosi, 2007); inappropriate and ineffective policies (Anyanwu, 2007); lack of integration of macroeconomic plans and the absence of harmonization and coordination of fiscal policy (Onoh, 2007); gross mismanagement/misappropriations of public funds (Okemini and Uranta, 2008); and lack of economic potential for rapid economic growth and development (Ogbole, 2010). Despite the emphasis placed on fiscal policy in the management of the economy the manufacturing sector inclusive, Nigerian economy is yet to come on the path of sound growth and development because of low input of manufacturing sector to the economy (GDP). This study is specifically interested in answering some questions. Has the use of fiscal policy measures improved manufacturing sector significantly over time? Is there any significant relationship between fiscal policy, input and output (capacity utilization) of manufacturing sector? Answering these questions will help to provide insight on the empirical impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector in Nigeria and as well assist the government in formulating appropriate policies that will enhance manufacturing industry in particular and the economic growth generally.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the impact of manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria.

Specific objectives are:

- i. To assess the impact manufacturing sector output on economic growth in Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the impact of exchange rate on economic growth.
- iii. To examine the effect of inflation on economic growth.
- iv. To investigate the relationship between interest rate and economic growth.

1.4 Research Questions

The study would also explore the following question:

- i. Does manufacturing sector output have any significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii. Does exchange rate have any significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria?
- iii. What is the significant effect of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria?
- iv. What is the relationship between interest rate and economic growth in Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypothesis

Ho₁: Manufacturing sector output has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Exchange rate does not have any significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Ho₃: Inflation rate does not have any significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Ho₄: Interest Rate has no significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study will contribute immensely in aiding the government, policy makers, economic planners, researchers and the academia generally. It will provide an insight and understanding to the government on how to be prudent in spending public funds that would bring about economic growth and development. It is also of immense help in providing an insight and knowledge to the general public, policy makers, economic planners, and manufacturing sector regulatory authorities on the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector in Nigeria. To the academia, the findings of the study will contribute to the available literature on the current scenario of manufacturing sector in Nigeria and its level of contribution to the GDP. Based on our empirical findings and analysis, the result of the study will be of immense benefit to researchers who will rely on their contributions to existing knowledge for further research. The findings of this research will assist monetary authorities in assessing the performance of the fiscal policy measures in Nigeria particularly in terms of their impact on the output of manufacturing sector. This work is also of immense benefit to the policy makers and economic planners in terms of using its findings in formulating and implementing appropriate policy measures towards accelerating economic growth through the manufacturing sector.

1.7 Scope of the Study

This study evaluates the effect of manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria. The analysis of the contribution of the manufacturing sector to the economic growth of Nigeria is restricted to the period between 1990 to 2023 using only relevant performance indicators such as manufacturing sector output, inflation rate and interest rate.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Manufacturing

Manufacturing Sector has generally been described and accepted as an engine of growth and development of any country. In modern economies, industrialization under industrial sector is widely conceived as a critical tool for accelerating economic growth and development. It serves as a channel for the production of goods and services, creation of massive employment opportunities and generation incomes (Olorunfemi, Tomola, Felix & Ogunleye, 2013). According to Adofu, Taiga & Tijani (2015), manufacturing is viewed as the production of merchandise for sale or use through the application of tools, machine, labour, chemical and biological formulation. It involves both handicraft of human activities and high tech through which raw materials are transformed or converted into finished product in large scale.

In modern economy today, the development of industries (industrialization) is extensively based on technological development of productive strategies.

In Nigeria, the history of manufacturing and industrial development reflect how a nation could neglect a vital sector via economic policy

inconsistencies and the abandonment of the agricultural sector for oil sector, which was the major economic base of the country due to the discovery of oil in commercial quantity in 1970s (Adeola, 2005). Ogbu (2012) contested that oil industry in Nigeria is not a major determinant of employment; hence, it has limited contributions to other sectors of the economy since the capacity is yet to be developed by the government to vigorously pursue the more value-added activities of the petrochemical value chain. Thus, the oil industry has overtime lacks technological spillover effects. For instance, the contribution of the manufacturing sector to economic growth in Nigeria before 1970s was 10%.

2.1.2 Structure of Nigerian Manufacturing Sector

Nigeria's manufacturing value added (MVA) of an estimated \$3.4 billion in 1985 ranks her as Africa's largest manufacturing economy after Egypt and twelfth among developing countries. Yet despite two decades of growth boosted by import substituting policies, Nigeria's manufacturing sector remains heavily import dependent. According to Opaluwa et al (2010), the Nigerian economy is under-industrialized and its capacity utilization is also low. They stated that the sector has become increasingly dependent on the external sector for import of non-labour input. This has been the inevitable outcome of a perverse incentive structure that accelerated the growth of import intensive consumer goods and light assembly industries contributing relatively little value-added under high protective walls while decelerating growth of local resource-based industries. For example,

the share of food and textile products in manufacturing output fell from 51% in 1973/74 to 36% in 1977/78, while the share of durable goods with low value added rose from 7% to 19% during the period. Within the durable goods sub-sector itself, the share of transport equipment, which has low value added, rose from about one-tenth of one percent to 11% during 1971/72- 1977/78. The net effect of this is that import dependency was fostered in the manufacturing sector in the 1970s.

2.1.3 Concept of Economic Growth

Economic growth generally refers to a sustained increase in per capital national income or output over a long period of time. It is an economic situation whereby the quantum of increase in national output must exceed the rate of growth in population (Olufemi & Omorogiwa, 2024). Economic growth is a long-term expansion of the productive potential of the economy. It means an increase in Real GDP, in other words, an increase in national output and national income. The real GDP is the market value of all goods and services produced in a nation during a specific time period. Real GDP measures a society's wealth by indicating how fast profits may grow and the expected return on capital. It is labelled "real" because each year's data is adjusted to account for changes in year-to-year prices.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

There are a range of competing theories to the study of economic growth, development and diversification. Each approach has its strength and weaknesses with different ideological, theoretical and empirical conclusions.

These theories include; the endogenous growth model and the neoclassical theory.

Endogenous Theory

This study is anchored on the endogenous growth model. The motivation for the endogenous growth model stems from the failure of the neoclassical theories to explain the sources of long run economic growth. The neoclassical theory failed to explain the intrinsic features of economies, which led an economy to grow over an extended period of time. Therefore, the neoclassical theory focuses on the dynamic process through which capital-labour ratio approaches long-run equilibrium. In the absence of technological change, all economies tend converge to zero growth.

Neoclassical Theory

The neoclassical theory upholds increase in gross domestic product as a short run term equilibrating process in which the economy approaches its long run equilibrium. The models of endogenous growth model have some common structural features with its neoclassical counterparts; across however, they differ considerably in their underlying assumptions and conclusions drawn. The most significant theoretical differences are based on the neoclassical assumption of diminishing marginal returns to capital investments that permits increased returns to scale in aggregate production, and as well focusing on externalities in determining the rate of return on capital investments.

2.3 Empirical Review

Different studies have been conducted on manufacturing capacity utilization, its determinants and how it impacts growth in different economies of the world. However, a number of such studies have been selected as essential for elaborating research done in the area of manufacturing capacity utilization.

Emmanuel & Saliu (2017) investigated the impact of manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1981- 2015 by employing ordinary least square (OLS) technique. The study utilized the following variables such as gross domestic product as the dependent variable while the independent variables include manufacturing output, government expenditure, investment rate and money supply in the investigation of the impact of manufacturing sector 46 on the Nigerian economic growth. The results showed that manufacturing output has positive effect on the growth of the Nigeria's economy. The results however, revealed that the major hazards facing the manufacturing sector in Nigeria include chemical hazards, physical hazard and psychosocial hazard.

Opara and Okoye (2023) examined the Impact of Bank Credit on Nigeria's Manufacturing Sector. The study was carried out using regression technique of the Ordinary Least Square. The OLS techniques was applied after determining stationarity of our variables using the ADF Statistic, as well as the cointegration of variables using the Johansen approach and discovered that the variables are stationary and have a long term relationship among the variables in the model. From the result of the OLS, it was observed bank credits to

manufacturing subsectors, Bank demand deposit, bank lending rate, exchange rate, workers incentives and employment generation have a positive impact on manufacturing subsectors in Nigeria, although, exchange rate was expected to be either positive or negative. From the regression analysis, the result show that bank credits to manufacturing subsectors, Bank demand deposit, bank lending rate, bank interest rate, exchange rate, workers incentives and employment generation are statistically significant in explaining inflation in Nigeria Based on the finding from the study, the following recommendations were made: The government should adequately finance the manufacturing subsector through Loans and advances to help businesspersons finance, expand and produce new goods thereby increasing rate of employment and enhancing economic growth.

2.4 Literature Gap

Premised on different findings, it is plausible to conclude that the relationship between manufacturing sector and economic growth is mixed and inconclusive, thereby establishing a gap in knowledge. In an attempt to closing the gap in knowledge, this study considered the developing economy of Nigeria for time series of thirty-three (33) years, spanning from 1990-2023, which prior studies are yet to consider, thereby closing currency/financial period gap.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Research design is the structure and strategy for investigating the relationship between the variables of the study. The research design adopted for this study will be Ex-post facto

research design. This is ideal for conducting social research when it is not possible or acceptable to manipulate the characteristics of human participant.

3.2 Model Specification

Following Beck, Levine and Loayza (2000), we include initial income to control for convergence effects and secondary school enrolment to capture human capital accumulation. Further, we include several policy variables, such as government expenditures as a share of GDP, the share of exports and imports in GDP, the inflation rate, the black market premium and the share of credit to the private sector by financial institutions in GDP. For the purpose of this research work the above model specification will be adopt and build upon. With this adjustment incorporated into the model, it can therefore be specified in the form expressed below.

$$GDP = f(MOT + EXR + INFR + IR)$$

The ARDL (p, q) model is stated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GDP_t = & \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta MOT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta INFR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta IR_{t-i} \\ & \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i MOT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_i INFR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_i \Delta IR_{t-i} + \phi ECT \\ & + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (3.5) \end{aligned}$$

Where $ECT_t = Y_t - \alpha_0 - \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_1 \Delta Y_{t-i} - \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_i \Delta X_{t-i}$ and $\phi = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_1 \Delta Y_{t-i} \dots \dots \dots (3.5)$

The Bound test procedure used equations 3.3 and 3.4 into 3.5 as:

$$\Delta Y_t = - \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \gamma_1 Y_t * \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_i \Delta X_{t-i} - \rho Y_{t-1} - \alpha - \sum_{i=0}^p \delta X_{t-i} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (3.6)$$

Where:

GDP = Real Gross Domestic Product;

MOT = manufacturing sector output

EXR = Exchange Rate;

INFR = Inflation rate;

IR = Interest rate;

Parameters = a₀, a₁, a₂, a₃, a₄, a₅;

U_t= Error term

From the specified model equation above, endogenous variable is GDP while the exogenous variables are manufacturing sector output, exchange rate, inflation rate and interest rate.

The model to be estimated is of the following linear form;

The econometric form of the model is;

$$GDP_t = b_0 + b_1 MOT_t + b_2 EXR_t + b_3 INFR_t + b_4 IR_t + U_t \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

Further, the work set out to present an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model of the relationship between selected components of population growth rate and unemployment in Nigeria.

Then we test the existence of level relationship as $\rho = 0$ and $\delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_k = 0$ where $\Delta =$ difference operator, $\alpha =$ the short term coefficient, $\beta =$ the long run coefficients $\mu =$ white noise error term.

Table 3.1: *apriori* Expectation

Dependent Variable: Economic Growth:

Variable	Direction of Effect
Manufacturing Sector Output	<i>Positive</i>
Exchange Rate	<i>Negative</i>
Inflation Rate	<i>Negative</i>
Interest Rate	<i>Positive</i>

3.4 Diagnostic Test of the Model

Diagnostic test of the model were carried out using, unit root test, co integration, error correction, coefficient of multiple determination, R² analysis of variance and Durbin Watson statistics

3.4.1 Unit Root Test

$$\Delta Y_T = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{T-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k a_j \Delta Y_{T-1} + \varepsilon_T \dots \tag{3.7}$$

where Δ is the first difference operator ε_T is random error term that is iid $k =$ no of lagged differences $Y =$ the variable. The unit root test

$$ADF_\tau = \frac{\hat{\alpha}}{SE(\alpha)} \dots \dots \dots (3.8)$$

is computed we shall compare it with the relevant critical value for the Dickey-Fuller Test. If the test statistic is greater (in absolute value) than the critical value at 5% or 1% level of significance, then the null hypothesis of $\alpha = 0$ is rejected and no unit root is present. If the variables are non-stationary at level form and integrated of the same order, this implies evidence of co-integration in the model.

3.3 Economic Apriori Expectation

The economic apriori expectations of the model are as follows:

To fully explore the data generating process, we first examined the time series properties of model variables using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test.

The ADF test regression equations with constant are:

is then carried out under the null hypothesis $\alpha = 0$ against the alternative hypothesis of $\alpha < 0$. Once a value for the test statistics

3.4.2 Test of Significance

The significance test were tested at 5% level of significance using the coefficients of the independent variables and following the Rule: Reject the Null hypothesis if the t-prob is less than 0.05, otherwise accept the Null hypothesis when t-prob is greater than 0.05 i.e. Reject if t-prob < 0.05, Accept if t-prob > 0.05

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1: Result

4.1.1 Unit Root Test

Table 4.2: Summary of ADF test results at 5% critical value

VARIABLE	ADF TEST STATISTICS	CRITICAL VALUE 5%	ORDER OF INTEGRATION	DECISION RULE
GDP	-3.027122	-2.957110	I~ (1)	Reject Ho
MOT	-3.581091	-2.957110	I~ (1)	Reject Ho
EXR	-3.526271	-2.957110	I~ (1)	Reject Ho
INFR	4.480443	-2.960411	I~ (0)	Reject Ho
IR	-3.249766	-2.954021	I~ (0)	Reject Ho

Source: Authors computation with E-views 2026

From table 4.1 above, Inflation Rate (INFR) and Interest Rate (IR) were integrated of order zero (I ~ (0)) as they were stationary at level form. While Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Manufacturing Sector Output (MOT), Exchange Rate (EXR) were not stationary at level form, but became stationary after first difference which implies that the variables (GDP), (MOT) AND (EXR) were integrated of order one (I ~ (1)). The decision is based on the fact the ADF statistics that is greater than the ADF critical values at 5%, we reject H₀ and conclude that the variables are stationary. Since the variables are integrated of order one and zero and none of the variables is integrated of

Table 4.1: Data Set on Real Gross Domestic Product, Manufacturing Sector Output, Exchange Rate, Inflation Rate and Interest Rate.

order two. We therefore, apply the ARDL bound co-integration test.

4.1.2 ARDL Bound Co-integration Test

A necessary condition for testing for ARDL bound co-integrating test is that each of the variables be integrated of either of order one or zero or both (Pesaran, Shin and Smith, 2001). Since all the variables are integrated of order one and zero, we proceeded to estimate the ARDL bound test. The null hypothesis of ARDL bound co-integration is that the variables are not cointegrated as against the alternative that they are cointegrated. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the F-statistics is greater than the upper bound critical values at chosen level of significance.

Table 4.2: ARDL Bound Co-integration (5% critical value) Test Result for the models

Model	F-Statistics	K	Significance level	Critical Bound Value	
				10 (Lower Bound)	11 (Upper Bound)
	4.297466	4	5%	2.56	3.49

Source: Author's Computation 2026

From table 4.2 the F-statistics for the model is 4.297466 and is greater than the upper (I1) bound of 3.49 at 5% level of significance. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a long run relationship between manufacturing sector and economic growth in Nigeria. Since there is a long run relationship, we therefore estimate the short run and long run ARDL analysis.

Table 4.3: Summary of Parsimonious Short Run Relationship Result between manufacturing sector and economic growth in Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Prob
CointEq(-1)*	-0.647889	0.104177	6.219099	0.0001

Source: Author's Computation 2026

From table 4.3 above; the coefficient of the error correction term (cointEQ) is statistically significant and carries the expected negative sign at 5% level of significant; revealing that a short run relationship exists between manufacturing sector and economic growth in Nigeria. The speed of adjustment is -0.647889

Table 4.4: Summary of Long Run Relationship between Manufacturing Sector and economic growth in Nigeria Result.

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MOT	12.37091	0.765474	16.16111	0.0000
EXR	-25.56088	21.89237	-1.167570	0.2701
INFR	111.8175	36.87695	3.032178	0.0126
IR	-988.3503	313.4017	-3.153621	0.0103
C	-5550.039	5753.786	-0.964589	0.3575

Source: Author's Computation 2026

4.1.5 Interpretation of Long Run ARDL Result

GDP = -5550.039 + 12.37091MOT - 25.56088EXR +111.8175INFR -988.3503IR

4.1.3 Test for Short Run Relationship

Having ascertained that there exist a co-integrating relationship between manufacturing sector and economic growth in Nigeria, the short run relationship needs to be ascertained.

that is 64% of the adjustment to equilibrium of the economic growth is expected to occur in short run.

4.1.4 Test for Long Run Relationship

It's imperative to ascertain the long run relationship that exists between manufacturing sector and economic growth in Nigeria.

The long run coefficient from table 4.4 above shows that the joint impact of all exogenous variables (MOT, EXR, INFR and IR) on the

endogenous variable will amount to -55.0 percent; this is on the basis that they are all held at constant. In other word if all the exogenous variables are held at constant it will amount to -55% contribution to economic growth in Nigeria.

Manufacturing Sector Output (MOT) possessed a positive relationship with economic growth in Nigeria with coefficient value of 12.3 percent; this entailing that on the long run, as Manufacturing Sector Output (MOT) increases by one percent, it causes 12.3 percent increase in economic growth in Nigeria. This conforms to apriori expectation

Exchange Rate (EXR) possessed a negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria with coefficient value of -25.5 percent; this entailing that on the long run, as Exchange Rate (EXR) increases by one percent, it causes 25 percent decrease in economic growth in Nigeria.

Inflation Rate (INFR) possessed a positive relationship with economic growth in Nigeria with coefficient value of 111.1 percent; this entailing that on the long run, as Inflation Rate (INFR) increases by one percent, it causes 111.1 percent increase in economic growth in Nigeria.

Interest Rate (IR) possessed a negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria with coefficient value of - 988.35 percent; this entailing that on the long run, as Interest Rate (IR) increases by one percent, it causes - 988.35 percent decrease in economic growth in Nigeria.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

The individual test was carried out to test for joint significance of the independent variables

on the dependent variable at 5% level using t-probability and t-statistic shown in table 4.5 and 4.6. The rule applied was: If t-probability is greater than the prescribed level of 5% or 0.05, accept the null hypothesis, otherwise reject the null hypothesis when f-probability is less than 0.05.

From table 4.4 above, the probability of t-stat of MOT was 0.0000, and less than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that Manufacturing Sector Output has a statistically significant relationship with Economic Growth in Nigeria. Also, Exchange Rate has no statistically significant relationship with Economic Growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, the probability of t-stat of INFR was 0.0126 and less than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that Inflation has a statistically significant relationship with Economic Growth in Nigeria. Finally, the probability of t-stat of IR was 0.0103 and less than 0.05 critical values. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that Interest Rate has a statistically significant relationship with Economic Growth in Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

This study examined the impact of manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria from 1990 to 2023; a period of 33 years. However, from the analysis it was discovered that manufacturing sector output has a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria both in the long run and short run. This conformed to apriori expectation. Exchange rate had a negative and statistically insignificant relationship with

economic growth while interest rate had a negative and statistically significant relationship with economic growth. Inflation rate had a positive and statistically significant relationship with economic growth. This result however, does not conform to apriori expectations. This study conformed to the works of Some researchers like Aminu et al (2019), who examined the nexus between manufacturing sector output and financial development and Emmanuel and Saliu (2017) who investigated the impact of manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1981- 2015. Thus, the study concluded that manufacturing sector can be effectively be used to improve the Nigerian economy and thus a veritable tool for growth and development.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The study examines specifically the impact of manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria. The following summarizes the result of the research work;

i. Manufacturing Sector Output had a positive and significant impact on economic growth.

ii. Exchange Rate has a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

iii. Inflation Rate has a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

iv. Interest Rate had a negative and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

This study examined the impact of the manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria from 1990-2023. The data used in this study were obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin of various issues (2023) and WDI (2023). These comprises of annual data of the following variables; Gross Domestic Product served as the dependent variable in the model while Manufacturing Sector Output, Exchange Rate, Inflation Rate and Interest Rate served as the independent variables. The test statistics used in the analysis was; Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL). The results showed that; Manufacturing Sector Output had a positive and significant impact on economic growth, Exchange Rate has a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria, and Inflation Rate has a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. Finally, Interest Rate had a negative and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. The study concluded that the manufacturing sector can be effectively be used to improve the Nigerian economy and thus a veritable tool for growth and development. In conclusion, the Nigerian economy has what it takes to achieve economic development and growth through the manufacturing sector, due to the fact that it will assist in employment generation, stimulation of entrepreneurship, mobilizing hidden capital in the economy, provide a level class of self-employed entrepreneurs, development and utilization of local and foreign technology, steaming rural-urban migration and encouragement of equitable distribution in

income and wealth. Finally, it is important to note the efforts made by the government to increase manufacturing sector output by increasing its expenditure on capital expenditure most especially electricity power supply, which is one of the major agenda of this present civilian government in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

The study recommends the following:

1. Government should continue to support industries in Nigeria by implementing policies that will be friendly for businesses to operate.
2. Government should continue to encourage achieving low inflation rates for

REFERENCES

Adebiyi, K.A., Charles-Owaba, O.E., & Waheed, M. A. (2006). "An Empirical Analysis of Airways Safety in Nigeria". *Journal of Research in Engineering*. 3 (2), 18-25.

Chete, L. N., Adeoti, J. O. & Ogundele, O. (2016). Industrial development and growth in Nigeria: Lessons and challenges. Learning to Compete. Working paper No.2.

Mankiw, G., Romer, D., and Weil, D. (1992). "A Contribution to the Empirics of Economic Growth". *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107(1), 407-37.

Omoke, P. C. (2010). Inflation and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 3 (2)

Pacheco-Lopez, P., and Thirlwall, A.P. (2013). A New Interpretation of Kaldor's First Growth Law for Open Developing

industries to operate successfully and continue to have an effect on economic growth.

3. The government should intensify efforts at improving physical infrastructure notably in power supply and make it more accessible to manufacturers to reduce self-supply of electricity which brings huge operating cost. The financial institutions in Nigeria should make effort to invest more in the manufacturing sector so that the manufacturers can have enough funds to invest in modern technologies, and computer-integrated manufacturing system.

Economies, University of Kent School of Economics Discussion Papers, KDPE.

Pettinger, T. (2017). *Mercantilism theory and examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.economicshelp.org/blog/17553/trade/mercantilism-theory-and-examples/>

Quaicoe, A., Aboagye, A. Q. Q., & Bokpin, G. A. (2017). Assessing the impact of export processing zones on economic growth in Ghana. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 42, 1150-1163

Rekiso, Z. S. (2017). Rethinking regional economic integration in Africa as industrialization mattered. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 43, 87-98

Robinson, J.C., and Shor, G.M. (1989). Business-Cycle Influences on Work-

- Related Disability in Construction and Manufacturing. *Milbank Q.*, 67(1), 92-113.
- Sherif, J.O. (2012). The Performance of Manufacturing Sector and Utilization Capacity www.slideshare.net/.../the-performance-of- in Nigeria. Manufacturing-sector-and-utilizationcapacity
- Sider H. (1985). Work-Related Accidents and the Production Process. *Journal of Hum. Resour.*, 20(1), 47-63.
- Solow, R. M. (1956). "A Contribution to the Theory of Economic Growth," *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, LXX, 65-94.
- Sustainable development goals: 17 goals to transform your world. Retrieved from <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/>
- Szirmai A (2009). Industrialization as a Countries, United Nations University - Maastricht Economic and Social Engine of Growth in Developing Research and Training Centre on Innovation and Technology Maastricht, The Netherlands.
- Szirmai, A. (2012). Industrialization as an engine of growth in developing countries, 1950
- Udah, E. B. (2010). Industrial Development, Electricity Crisis and Economic Performance in Nigeria. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, ISSN 1450-2887 issue 18(1), 113-115.
- Viscusi, W.K. (1986). The Impact of Occupational Safety and Health Regulation, 1973-1983. *RAND Journal of Econ.*, 17(4), 567-580.
- Wakeford, J. J., Gebreyesus, M., Ginbo, T., Yimer, K., Manzambi, O., Okereke, C., Black, M., & Mulugetta, M. (2017). Innovation for green industrialization: An empirical assessment of innovation in Ethiopia's cement, leather and textile sectors. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 166, 503-511
- Yu, X., Dosi, G., & Grazz, M., & Lei, J. (2017). Inside the virtuous circle between productivity, profitability, investment and corporate growth: An anatomy of Chinese industrialization. *Research Policy*, 46, 1020-1038